

ELIXIR Commissioned Service [Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens (BFSP), WP3]

D3.1 Workflow available on UseGalaxy Europe and UseGalaxy France servers as well as published on IWC and WorkflowHub.

Tier: Science

Priority Area: Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens (BFSP)

Executive Summary

This deliverable aims to make the optimized workflow for building Metagenome-Assembled Genomes (MAGs) publicly available, in accordance with FAIR principles.

The workflow was successfully updated, optimized, and tested using both small test datasets and large datasets from the CAMI challenge. It is now available on the UseGalaxy Europe and UseGalaxy France servers. Additionally, the workflow was published on the Intergalactic Workflow Commission (IWC) and automatically cross-posted on WorkflowHub. The IWC update framework ensures the workflow remains continuously updated with the latest tool versions.

Disseminating the workflow via public Galaxy servers enables its usability in large-scale MAG analysis projects using public computational resources. This accessibility minimizes usage barriers, even for researchers without bioinformatics expertise.

Document info

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Dissemination level	Public

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

MAGs	Metagenome-Assembled Genomes
IWC	Intergalactic Workflow Commission
CAMI	Critical Assessment of Metagenome Interpretation

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Workflow optimization

All tools and databases were successfully updated to the latest versions. Taxonomy classification using GTDB-tk ¹ (v2.4.0) and genome annotation using Bakta ² (v1.9.4) for the generated MAGs were added to the workflow. The bin refinement tool DAS Tool ³ was changed to Binette ⁴ (v1.0.5), which yielded better results in a Benchmark using the CAMI II Marine Dataset ⁵.

Figure 1: F1 (Mean of completeness and purity) score for different Bidders based on the CAMI II marine dataset. Binette yielded the highest score using the pooled CAMI II marine dataset.

The workflow was adapted to allow the usage of two different assembly tools: MEGAHIT⁶ (v1.2.9) and metaSPADES⁷ (v4.2.0).

Required metadata about License, Creators, and Annotations was added to the workflow. In order to facilitate the testing of the workflow, a minimal input dataset was created containing reads that lead to the creation of one small MAG (<https://zenodo.org/records/15089018>).

The workflow was successfully benchmarked using the CAMI II infrastructure, yielding 65 MAGs with more than 75 % completeness for the Marine Dataset.

¹ Chaumeil et al., "GTDB-Tk V2."

² Schwengers et al., "Bakta."

³ Sieber et al., "Recovery of Genomes from Metagenomes via a Dereplication, Aggregation and Scoring Strategy."

⁴ Mainguy and Hoede, "Binette."

⁵ Meyer et al., "Critical Assessment of Metagenome Interpretation."

⁶ Li et al., "MEGAHIT."

⁷ Bankevich et al., "SPAdes."

Figure 2: Completeness vs Contamination plot. Completeness vs Contamination of the MAGs found for the CAMI II Marine dataset, colored by Phylum.

Workflow publication

The workflow is available via IWC

(<https://iwc.galaxyproject.org/workflow/mags-building-main/>). From this landing page, the workflow can be executed (including test data) on any public Galaxy instances or downloaded for usage in a local instance. Currently, all required tools and databases are available on UseGalaxy Europe (usegalaxy.eu) and UseGalaxy France (usegalaxy.fr).

The workflow is also available via WorkflowHub⁸ (<https://workflowhub.org/workflows/1352>), Dockstore⁹

(<https://dockstore.org/workflows/github.com/iwc-workflows/mags-building/main>), and Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/records/15711334>).

The IWC update framework has already updated a set of tools to their latest versions, yielding version 0.3 of the workflow (<https://github.com/galaxyproject/iwc/pull/826> and <https://github.com/galaxyproject/iwc/pull/895>).

List of figures (generated using a script available on the project GitHub repository:

https://github.com/usegalaxy-eu/FAIRyMAGs/blob/main/Analysis_Scripts/benchmark.ipynb)

- Figure 1: F1 (Mean of completeness and purity) score for different Binner based on the CAMI II marine dataset.
- Figure 2: Completeness vs Contamination plot. Completeness vs Contamination of the MAGs found for the CAMI II Marine dataset colored by Phylum.

⁸Gustafsson et al., "WorkflowHub."

⁹Yuen et al., "The Dockstore."

Outcomes and expected impact

This deliverable is fully aligned with the primary objective of disseminating a robust metagenomics workflow for constructing Metagenome-Assembled Genomes (MAGs) using the Galaxy platform. By making the workflow available through Galaxy, researchers are equipped with both the technical tools and computational resources needed to carry out such analyses independently. A key strength of this workflow is its ability to be easily adapted to specific research goals with minimal technical expertise required. As a result, we expect it to have a significant impact on the rapidly expanding field of novel microbial community analysis—an impact already anticipated and exemplified through the independent analysis of use cases outlined in D3.2.

Dissemination Plans

The publication of the workflow in IWC ensures wide dissemination via various channels (IWC, WorkflowHub, Dockstore and Zenodo), including continuous updates with every tool update. The latest version will also be featured in a final publication, which includes the benchmark, training, and selected use cases.